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Road Guard: AI-Powered Road Damage Detection and Reporting System

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ABSTRACT

Potholes pose a significant challenge to road safety and infrastructure maintenance, demanding efficient solutions for detection and reporting. This paper presents an automated system for real-time pothole detection and reporting, leveraging the YOLOv8 object detection model and GPS integration for accurate location tracking. A Flask-based web application provides an organized platform to manage detected pothole data, classify severity levels such as Critical or Average, and store information in a JSON file for persistent access. Additionally, an interactive map feature enables authorities to filter, view, and manage pothole records efficiently. The proposed system demonstrates a practical approach to improve road condition monitoring and maintenance.

Keywords:-*YOLOv8, GPS tracking, Flask web application, Severity classification, Interactive mapping, Road infrastructure management*

1. INTRODUCTION

Road infrastructure maintenance poses a persistent challenge worldwide, with potholes emerging as one of the most critical issues affecting road safety. In India, potholes contributed over 4,446 road accidents in 2022 [1], imposing significant economic burden through vehicle repairs and maintenance costs. The situation is severe in urban areas where heavy traffic, monsoon seasons, and inadequate drainage systems contribute to road surface deterioration [2]. These hazards become even more perilous during the rainy season, as waterlogged potholes become difficult to see, posing a significant risk, particularly for two-wheeler riders.

Traditional pothole management mostly depends on manual checks and citizen reports, which makes it slow to respond to worsening road conditions. These methods often lead to slow response times, poor use of resources, and inconsistent records of road conditions. Without a standard way to classify severity or monitor conditions in real-time, authorities struggle to prioritize repairs and use resources effectively. Even with rising infrastructure budgets, traditional identification and repair methods can't keep up with road degradation, leading to a growing backlog that threatens public safety and strains economic resources.

Recent advancement in computer vision and machine learning has significantly improved automated road condition monitoring [3]. Advanced object detection models like YOLOv8 (You Only Look Once) allow for quick and accurate detection of road defects. By integrating these models with modern web technologies and GPS, we can create smarter and more effective ways to find and manage potholes. To address these challenges, we propose an automated pothole detection and reporting system. This system would utilize advanced computer vision and machine learning technologies

to identify and report road deterioration. Our solution integrates a Jetson Nano platform with a YOLO object detection model, enabling real-time pothole identification from continuous video streams. The system automatically classifies detected potholes based on severity [4] and pinpoints their location using GPS. It uses a Flask-based web framework for backend operations [5], and the collected data is presented through interactive maps on a dashboard powered by Leaflet.js [6]. The system is designed to manage data efficiently, allowing authorized personnel to easily access, update, and analyze pothole information. This automation replaces the traditional manual pothole detection process and offers a scalable way to monitor roads in different cities, moreover the severity classification algorithms helps prioritize road conditions based on damage.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section II reviews existing works in automated pothole detection and management systems. Section III outlines our proposed methodology, covering dataset preparation, implementation of the YOLOv8 model, and the overall system architecture. In Section IV, we present our experimental results and evaluate the system's performance based on established metrics. Section V covers detailed discussion of our findings, addresses current limitations, and explores potential future enhancements. Finally, Section VI wraps up with a summary of our key contributions and looks at how this research can impact urban infrastructure management and smart city applications.

2. RELATED WORK

Various types of pothole detection systems have been introduced in recent years, which can be broadly classified into traditional methods and automated approaches. Traditional pothole

detection often relies on manual inspections and citizen reports, which are time-consuming and prone to inaccuracies. In contrast, automated approaches use image processing techniques, sensor-based systems, and artificial intelligence to improve efficiency and accuracy in detecting road damage.

Among them Monitoring of Road Damage Detection Systems Using Image Processing Methods and Google Map [7], Sulistyowati et al. (2021) introduced a road damage detection system that works in conjunction with Google Maps to improve driver safety. Their system utilizes the Werner D. Streidt algorithm along with edge detection techniques to identify potholes. The implementation utilized RaspberryPi 2 as data management centers, equipped with a 6M NEO U-box GPS sensor for geotagging locations and a CSI camera for capturing road surface. The system's pothole detection success rate was 83.2% in sunny conditions but fell to 67% when tree barriers were present. A significant aspect of their work was the real-time integration with Google Maps, marking all detected pothole locations in the application. Overall, the research demonstrates the practical application of affordable embedded systems for infrastructure monitoring. However, further efforts are necessary to ensure reliable detection rates in various environmental conditions.

In **The Assay of Potholes and Road Damage Detection** [8], where Kumar et al. (2022) proposed an innovative smartphone-based application designed to assist the government bodies like the National Highways Authority of India (NHAI) and municipal corporations in road maintenance work. Their system uses machine learning-based object detection model to detect potholes in user-submitted images, and storing the data on a

centralized server for authority access. The system incorporates Firebase Cloud Messaging for notifications, Google Analytics to track usage patterns, and Firebase Authentication for a secure user management. While their approach effectively connects citizens with road maintenance authorities through a crowdsourced reporting system, its reliance on manual image capture limits and real-time monitoring capabilities. Their work highlights the potential of using common smartphone technology for infrastructure monitoring, though managing upload limits is necessary to ensure data traffic does not overwhelm the system, which could hinder its overall effectiveness.

In **Image-Based Pothole Detection Using Multi-Scale Feature Network and Risk Assessment** [4], Heo et al. (2023) addressed the challenges of real-time pothole detection on low-spec hardware systems by developing SPFPN-YOLOv4 tiny, an enhanced version of YOLOv4 tiny that incorporates spatial pyramid pooling and feature pyramid network with CSPDarknet53-tiny. Their approach resulted in a 2-5% improvement in mean average precision compared to conventional YOLO models, achieving an accuracy of 79.6% on their test dataset. A notable aspect of their research was the introduction of a risk assessment algorithm that evaluates pothole severity by comparing the tire contact patch size with the actual pothole dimensions using pinhole camera and distance estimation equations. This risk classification system categorizes potholes into three levels: danger, caution, and safe, prioritizing repairs based on the severity of road damage. The system achieved real-time performance at 38 FPS using CPU processing solely, making it suitable for vehicular systems. However, while their visual risk indication system marks dangerous potholes with red bounding

boxes, they noted the need for additional haptic and vibration signals to alert driver.

In Pothole detection in the woods: a deep learning ap- proach for forest road surface monitoring with dashcams

[9] by Hoseini et al.(2023)made significant advancements in the area of pothole detection specifically on forest roads. Their research utilizes a YOLOv5 model combined with StrongSORT tracking to detect and monitor potholes using consumer-grade dashcams. This approach is remarkable due to its effectiveness in the difficult conditions often encountered on forest roads and across diverse weather scenarios. Their system achieved impressive detection performance with precision and recall rates of 0.79 and 0.58 respectively, and a mean average precision of 0.70 at an IoU threshold of 0.5. This research is highly valuable and cost-efficient solution for forest road maintenance, leveraging readily accessible technology while ensuring reliable detection accuracy in challenging environments.

The **POT-YOLO: Real-Time Road Potholes Detection using Edge Segmentation based Yolo V8 Network** [10], Bhavana et al. (2024) introduced a novel approach to detect various road defects including cracks, oil stains, patches, and pebbles using an enhanced

YOLOv8 architecture. Their system processes pothole videos through a multi-stage approach, using Contrast Stretching Adaptive Gaussian Star Filter (CAGF) to reduce distortions and Sobal edge detector for pothole identification before final YOLOv8 detection. The system achieved impressive results with 99.10% accuracy, outperforming existing networks like Faster RCNN, SSD, and mask R-CNN. The authors noted limitations in handling image quality and lighting conditions, suggesting future work in al- gorithm optimization and pothole severity measurement. Their research represents a significant advancement in automated pothole detection systems for road safety improvement.

3. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The proposed system presents a simple and effective way to maintain roads by automatically detecting and reporting pot- holes. Using the YOLOv8 deep learning model combined with computer vision and GPS tracking, the system provides a real- time road condition monitoring solutions. The system detects potholes, assesses their severity, and displays this information on a web dashboard, enabling authorities to efficiently manage road maintenance operations.

Fig.1:-Proposed Architecture

As shown in Figure 1, The system architecture consists of five main stages working together efficiently. Starting with acquiring well-defined dataset suitable for training. The system then uses this dataset to train a YOLOv8 model optimized for pothole detection. The real-time detection stage handles detection process through a camera module and the data processing stage manages the detected potholes assessing their severity and simultaneously capturing GPS locations. Finally, the visualization stage displays a web dashboard that offers information about each detected pothole and its locations.

System Components Overview

The pothole detection and reporting system integrates hardware and software for effective real-time monitoring and data collection. The hardware architecture consists of a camera mounted on a vehicle, such as a government or public transport vehicle, which captures continuous road footage. The system runs on an NVIDIA Jetson Orion, a powerful device for edge computing tasks. A GPS module is integrated to obtain the accurate location of identified potholes.

On the software side, the system employs YOLOv8, a deep learning model by Ultralytics to detect potholes in the video frames. Information about the potholes, including their severity classification, is stored permanently in a JSON file which acts as a lightweight and structured database. A Flask-based web dashboard allows authorities to access pothole information on an interactive map using Leaflet.js.

A. Dataset Acquisition and Training

The dataset for pothole detection consist 1,036 training images and 115 testing images, collected from diverse road environments including highways, city roads, and rural areas. We used multiple sources for the images, such as

smartphones, dashcams, and CCTV cameras, to ensure we had a diverse range of perspectives for comprehensive model training. The dataset was pre-labeled with bounding box coordinates in a format compatible with YOLOv8, so we didn't have to spend time on manual annotation, making the training process a lot more convenient.

The detection workflow analyzes incoming video streams frame-by-frame. It uses a confidence threshold to ensure that only those detections with a score higher than 0.5 are registered in the system. This approach helps to filter out false positives while maintaining detection sensitivity. The threshold of 0.5 was chosen based on testing to find the right balance between accuracy and reliability in the system.

This system utilizes a NEO-6M GPS module that is integrated with the Jetson Orion platform for geospatial integration. When a pothole is detected, the system immediately captures the exact GPS coordinates, giving immediate spatial references for each identified road damage. This synchronized method of tracking ensures that every pothole being captured is mapped to its specific location simultaneously for efficient monitoring and maintenance of the roads.

Here, the practical approach to classify the severity of potholes is done by using a composite Severity Index (SI). This index is calculated by considering three essential parameters: The normalized area (A) of the pothole, an estimated depth of the pothole (D), and its edge characteristics (E). By combining these elements with specific weights, the system can accurately predict how serious each pothole is, by the equation 1:

$$SI = w_1A + w_2D + w_3E \quad (1)$$

where w_1 , w_2 , and w_3 represent the weighted coefficients, while A, D, and E are normalized parameters bounded

between 0 and 1. The classification thresholds to classify data, are defined in Equation 2:

$$\text{Classification} = \begin{cases} \text{Critical,} & \text{if } SI \geq 0.7 \\ \text{Average,} & \text{if } 0.3 \leq SI < 0.7 \end{cases}$$

Fig.2:- Sample Images from Pothole Detection Dataset

(2)The training implementation utilized the YOLOv8n model from Ultralytics, selected for its efficient and lightweight architecture. The model training was conducted on Google Co- lab's GPU-accelerated environment, opting to train the model from scratch instead of starting with pre-trained weights. The training started with an initial 100 epochs, followed by an additional 200 epochs for fine-tuning. This iterative training approach enhanced the model's detection accuracy and robustness, making it suitable for real-world pothole detection applications.

B. Data Processing and analysis

This study outlines a data processing pipeline that starts with capturing video in real time and ends with organizing information about potholes. The system leverages the YOLOv8n neural network architecture, which has been specifically trained for pothole detection in dynamic road conditions. This advanced technology was selected by analyzing its capability Potholes with an SI value of 0.7 or higher are labeled as Critical, indicating their bad condition and need urgent repairs because they can pose serious safety risks for drivers. On the other hand, potholes that fall between 0.3 to 0.7 in SI values are considered as Average representing

moderate deterioration, while they should be kept an eye on it but don't need an immediate action. This binary classification system facilitates to take decision according to time.

The processed data is stored permanently in an structured JSON format, facilitating standardized data management and easy integration. Each pothole record contains essential details, including a unique ID, geographical coordinates, location context, severity classification, and time-related data. This approach make it easier to retrieve and analyze information while allowing smooth integration with geographic Informa- tion systems (GIS) for mapping and visualization. As we can analyze when and where the potholes occur, it helps in planning better road maintenance and allocating resources effectively. The entire processing pipeline operates in real- time, with minimal latency between detection and data storage. This quick response makes the system practical for continuous road monitoring. The integration of GPS coordinates with detection events creates a detailed database of road conditions, which offers valuable insights for infrastructure maintenance and urban planning.

```
{  
  "id": 1,  
  "Latitude": 12.000541542442033,  
  "Longitude": 75.34217565254397,  
  "City": "Taliparamba",  
  "Severity": "Critical",  
  "DateTime": "2025-01-26 16:53:55"  
}
```

Fig.3:-Json structure format

C. Web Dashboard

Fig.4:-Dashboard

We developed an interactive web dashboard (Figure. 5) that lets the user to monitor pothole detections in real-time across multiple cities. The dashboard shows the potholes on a map and provides detailed information about each detection, making it easy for authorities to track and manage road conditions.

The backend of the system is built using Flask, a lightweight Python web framework, with Cross-Origin Resource Sharing (CORS) support for handling client requests. The server is responsible for managing data related to pothole detection, using a JSON-based storage system. It has various endpoints that allow retrieving, filtering, and managing data. To enhance performance, the architecture is

threaded allowing it to handle multiple detection simulations and client requests simultaneously. Additionally, there are signal handlers ensuring smooth system shut down. On the frontend, the system utilizes Leaflet.js for geographical visualization showcasing detected potholes on an interactive map. The interface features a city selection dropdown, enabling users to narrow their focus onto a specific urban area. Pothole markers on the map are color-coded based on severity levels - red representing critical conditions and blue for average conditions. Each marker provides detailed information through popup windows, including detection timestamp and precise coordinates.

Fig.5:-Potholes classified based on severity

The dashboard's user interface is divided into three main components: the city selection dropdown, an interactive map, and dual lists categorizing critical and average severity pot- holes. This layout allows maintenance teams to prioritize their work effectively. Each pothole entry shows important details about the detected pothole and includes a handy option to remove the entry from the list once the pothole has been repaired. Real-time data updates are achieved through periodic API checks, ensuring the dashboard reflects the latest detection results. This system uses advanced AI technology (YOLO) to identify potholes in video footage. When a pothole is detected, the information is immediately available on the dashboard. The system is smart enough to only report potholes it's fairly confident about, helping to reduce the number of false alarms and ensuring that teams can trust the reports they receive.

4. TESTING, VALIDATION AND RESULTS

Our pothole detection system was implemented and evaluated using a comprehensive hardware and software configuration. The NVIDIA Jetson Orin served as the main processing unit for real-time detection. Location data was captured using a NEO-6M GPS module, while a CMOS-based camera with a 170° interior and 110° exterior field of view monitor road conditions. This camera

setup mounted on a vehicle, recorded in 1080p at 30 fps with night vision capability for low- light conditions. On the software side, the system ran in a Linux environment using Python 3.12.2 and uses YOLOv8 by Ultralytics for object detection.

The trained YOLOv8n model demonstrated strong detection capabilities across various testing conditions. It achieved a mean Average Precision of 0.7763. Further analysis of the model's performance revealed a precision of 0.7282, recall of 0.7553, and an F1-score of 0.7415. These balanced metrics indicate that the model effectively minimizes both false positives and false negatives, which is beneficial for practical implementation. The precision value shows approximately 73% of detected potholes were true positives, while the recall value indicates that around 76% of actual potholes present in test images were detected successfully.

The confusion matrix (Figure. 6) depicts how well the model performed. It shows the breakdown of true positives, false positives, true negatives, and false negatives, which helps us understand the model's overall accuracy in detecting different outcomes in the test dataset.

The web dashboard performed exceptionally well during testing, with the Flask backend efficiently processing pothole

Fig.6:-Confusion Matrix

Fig.7:-*Detection under specific conditions*

infrastructure using computer vision and IoT technologies. By integrating a YOLOv8-based detection algorithm with GPS tracking and a user-friendly web dashboard, we have created a comprehensive tool for government officials to identify, track, and manage road surface defects effectively. The Flask-based backend efficiently processes pothole data, while the map visualization feature support both comprehensive and targeted monitoring approaches through city-based filtering.

Despite its limitations, such as adverse weather conditions, hardware limitations, data storage capability, the system presents a significant improvement over traditional manual inspection methods. This automated approach not only reduces the burden on maintenance teams but also has the potential to speed up response times for urgent repairs.

This research contributes to the growing field of smart city infrastructure management by highlighting how machine learning and web technologies can work together to solve real-life problems. Future enhancements focusing on adaptability to environmental changes, analyzing data over time, and integrating with existing municipal systems. As cities continue to face infrastructure

maintenance challenges with limited budgets, technology-driven solutions like this pothole detection system will be crucial in optimizing resource use and improving road safety for citizens data under normal load conditions. The map visualization handled large datasets smoothly, and city-based filtering improved speed and focus. These results validated the system’s effectiveness in supporting municipal maintenance teams for real-time pothole monitoring and management, potentially improving response times for repairs and overall urban infrastructure management.

Despite the system’s promising performance, several limitations were identified during testing. For instance, the YOLOv8 model’s detection accuracy reduced under poor lighting conditions or heavy rain due to water reflections and visual distortions. The camera’s field of view (170° interior and 110° exterior) occasionally failed to capture smaller potholes near edges of the frame. The JSON-based data storage method also struggles with larger datasets, slowing down high-speed queries. Looking ahead, to address these limitations we planned to tackle it through several strategies. Our goal is to expand the training dataset to include diverse weather and lighting conditions. Additionally, we aim to

implement temporal analysis across video frames to reduce both false positives and false negatives. Additionally, switching to more robust database solution will allow better scalability, especially for city-wide implementations.

Finally, we intend to develop predictive analytics for pothole deterioration patterns, for proactive maintenance recommendations and further improve the system's practical utility, enhancing effectiveness for managing urban infrastructure.

5. CONCLUSION

The pothole detection and reporting system developed in this project demonstrates an innovative way to monitor urban

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